

Phase-space spirals in Gaia DR 2: the role of the Milky Way bar

Sergey Khoperskov^{1,2,3}, Paola Di Matteo³, Ortwin Gerhard¹, David Katz³,
Misha Haywood³, Françoise Combes^{4,5}, Peter Berczik^{6,7,8}, Ana Gomez³

¹ Max Planck Institute for Extraterrestrial Physics, 85741 Garching, Germany

² Institute of Astronomy, Russian Academy of Sciences, 48 Pyatnitskya St., Moscow 119017, Russia

³ GEPI, Observatoire de Paris, PSL Université, CNRS, 5 Place Jules Janssen, 92190 Meudon, France

⁴ Observatoire de Paris, LERMA, CNRS, PSL Univ., UPMC, Sorbonne Univ., F-75014, Paris, France

⁵ College de France, 11 Place Marcelin Berthelot, 75005, Paris, France

⁶ Astronomisches Rechen-Institut, Zentrum für Astronomie der Universität Heidelberg, Monchhofstr. 12-14, D-69120 Heidelberg, Germany

⁷ National Astronomical Observatories of China, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Datun Lu 20A, Chaoyang District, Beijing 100012, China

⁸ Main Astronomical Observatory, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Akademika Zabolotnoho 27, 03680 Kyiv, Ukraine

Abstract

Using a single N -body simulation we explore the formation, evolution, and spatial variation of the phase-space spirals similar to those recently discovered in the Milky Way disk. For the first time in the literature we use a self-consistent N -body simulation of an isolated Milky Way-type galaxy to show that the phase-space spirals develop naturally from vertical waves driven by the buckling of the stellar bar. Such vertical oscillations trigger the formation of various time-dependent phase-space spirals in the entire disk. The underlying physical mechanism implies the link between in-plane and vertical motion that leads directly to phase-space structures whose amplitude and shape are in remarkable agreement with those of the phase-space spirals observed in the Milky Way disk. In our isolated galaxy simulation, phase-space spirals are still distinguishable at the solar neighborhood 3 Gyr after the buckling phase. The long-lived character of the phase-space spirals generated by the bar buckling instability cast doubts on the timing argument used so far to get back to the time of the onset of the perturbation.

1 Introduction

Gaia Data Release 2 provided to the community an unprecedented amount of high-quality knowledge about kinematics and spatial structures of the Milky Way disk and its surroundings (Gaia Collaboration et al., 2018a). In particular, the second data release (DR2) contains the full six-dimensional phase-space information for 7.2 million stars, which made possible several discoveries about kinematics and the spatial structure of our Galaxy (Gaia Collaboration et al., 2018b). It has become abundantly clear that non-equilibrium processes in the Milky Way such as satellite interactions, bar dynamics, and spiral structure effects have shaped the present-day structure and kinematics of the Milky Way significantly. One of the most striking new features discovered is the spiral-like distributions in the $z - v_z$ plane, which suggest that the Milky Way disk is locally out of dynamical equilibrium. In particular, Antoja et al. (2018) found spirals in the distribution of radial and azimuthal velocities in $z - v_z$ plane for stars that lie in a small volume around the Sun (< 0.1 kpc). By combining Gaia DR2 with spectroscopic surveys such as GALAH (Bland-Hawthorn et al., 2019) and LAMOST (Tian et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2019), this result has been quickly confirmed to hold also in a more extended volume of the Milky Way disk.

Internal processes, external tides, and local galaxy disk perturbations are the main physical factors that

could be responsible for the observed phase-space mixing process in the solar neighborhood (see e.g., Trick et al., 2019; Michtchenko et al., 2019; Cheng et al., 2019; Fragkoudi et al., 2019; Monari et al., 2018). For instance, Laporte et al. (2019) claim that last pericentric passage of Sagittarius-like dSph resets the formation of the local present-day phase-space snail and situate its formation around 500-800 Myr (see also Antoja et al., 2018; Binney & Schönrich, 2018). Li & Shen (2019) suggested that the more prominent snail shell in azimuthal velocity distribution is due partly to the fact that only the colder orbits exhibit the phase space spiral. Despite a number of successful studies we still do not know the dominant cause of the observed deviations from equilibrium state of the Milky Way disk. In this work, we draw our attention to understanding of the phase-space spiral structure formation due to an internal processes, in particular due to the bar buckling instability.

2 Model and results

In order to investigate the phase-space mixing in the Milky Way type galaxy, we performed a single, extremely high-resolution, N -body simulation of disk galaxy evolution embedded into a live dark matter halo. We adopted the initial conditions from a recent study of the bar/bulge regions of the Milky Way by Fragkoudi et al. (2017) and details are also presented in Khoperskov et al. (2019).

Figure 1: Face-on map (30x30 kpc box) of the vertical offset in the simulated galaxy 3 Gyr after the vertical bar-buckling instability ($T = 4$ Gyr). Ring-like structures signal the non-steady wave propagating outwards across the disk with a vertical amplitude of 200 pc between red and blue colour. Black contours represent the stellar density distribution.

The global evolution of our simulated galaxy is in good agreement with many previous N -body models in which bars are usually weakened by the buckling instability (see, e.g., Raha et al., 1991; Combes et al., 1990; Debattista et al., 2004; Athanassoula, 2005). In our simulation, the initially axisymmetric disk develops a prominent bar in about two-three rotation periods. Between about 0.5 and 1 Gyr, the bar becomes vertically unstable and buckles, breaking the symmetry with respect to the equatorial disk midplane (see Fig. 1). After ≈ 1.2 Gyr, the bar profile across the disk plane becomes again symmetric, but the inner disk region now has a larger vertical thickness, and its isodensity-contours show a clear boxy morphology.

We may state that, so far, in relation to the study of the bar buckling process, attention has mostly been drawn to collective phenomena associated with the formation of bulges, while its possible impact on the outer disk regions – that is essentially outside the bar corotation – has not received particular attention. The bending instability has been associated with nonlinear processes during the bar evolution. The growth of the bar involves stars with low-velocity dispersion from the outer to inner regions, where the disk is already significantly hotter. Such a kinematical pressure anisotropy appears to drive the fire-horse instability across the bar (Raha et al., 1991), which in turn leads to the thickening of the disk, as a way to remove the source of instability in the disk. In addition to this, we find that the process of the ver-

tical bar instability (see Fig. 1) is also reflected in the kinematical properties of stars in the outer (relative to the bar) disk.

As follows from our simulation, indeed the development of the boxy/peanut structure also affects the disk areas outside the bar region. During the early linear phase of the bar growth (< 0.5 Gyr) our model is stable against the bending instability at all radii. However, once the disk starts to buckle and the bar strength decreases, bending waves appear initially in the central part of the disk, the bar region, forming bell-like structures, which later propagate farther out toward the galactic outskirts. After a relatively short vertical impulse in which the edge of the buckling bar acts as a source of bending waves, quasi-stationary ring-like structures are established over the entire outer galaxy. In particular, a symmetric $m = 0$ perturbation moves outward, and its amplitude weakly increases in the outer parts of the disk (see Fig. 1). It takes roughly 0.5 Gyr for perturbations to reach the outer disk part (> 10 kpc). Such a bending wave propagation process is very much similar to those found in a number of various theoretical and numerical works about the excitation of internally driven bending waves in the galactic disks (see, e.g., Hunter & Toomre, 1969; Kulsrud et al., 1971; Merritt & Sellwood, 1994; Khoperskov et al., 2010; Rodionov & Sotnikova, 2013; Khoperskov & Bertin, 2017; Chequers & Widrow, 2017).

The consequences of the bar buckling can persist over a significant time – more than 10 rotational periods at the solar radius – and it can have observational counterparts in the (z, v_z) phase-space distribution. Indeed, independent of the mechanism, the bending waves propagating across the disk suppress the mixing process in the phase space. It is thus natural to investigate the kind of features left by this mechanism in the $z - v_z$ plane. In order to compare our simulation with the results by Antoja et al. (2018), in Fig. 2 we present the phase-space mixing patterns in the disk at $R = 8$ kpc from the center in a small arc of 15° of 1 kpc radial width oriented with 30° relative to the bar. This region contains of about 547856 to 624231 particles at different times. At early times, before the perturbation from the buckling bar reaches the solar radius, (z, v_z) phase-space structure is highly symmetric in the innermost part (low $|z|$ and $|v_z|$), and only a weak quadrupole pattern dominates in the outer region of the distribution. Such a picture is known as a tilt of the velocity ellipsoid (see, e.g., Section 5.1 in Bland-Hawthorn et al., 2019, and references therein), which is the manifestation of a fully mixed galactic disk. Once the vertical perturbations arrive at the outer disk regions ($T \approx 0.5$ Gyr), in the $v_r(z, v_z)$ distribution, we start to observe an asymmetric two-arm spiral structure in (z, v_z) -plane, which corresponds to a transition phase between a tilted ellipse and a single arm spiral. Figure 2 (top row) demonstrates a clear similarity to the Gaia-like phase-space spiral at $T = 1.3$ Gyr. The spiral structure is more clearly seen in the distribution of radial velocity (z, v_z) space at early times but later it is more evident in azimuthal velocity distribution. Thus we find that internally driven bending waves trigger a clear correlation between in-plane and vertical motions that lead to spiral structures that are in good agreement to the phase-space spirals observed at the solar neighbor-

Figure 2: Phase-space spiral in $z - v_z$ plane for a solar neighborhood-like region in the disk, at $R = 8$ kpc; top row for a single moment of $T = 1.3$ Gyr, for bottom row $T = 4$ Gyr. The bar is rotated by 30 degrees relative to the direction on the galactic center. Left: the mean radial velocity, and right: the mean residual azimuthal velocity $v_\varphi(z, v_z) - \langle v_\varphi(z, v_z) \rangle$.

hood.

Surprisingly, the phase-space spiral pattern is still visible in a solar neighborhood-like region at later times ($T > 1.5$ Gyr, see bottom row of Fig. 2) after the end of the boxy/peanut bulge formation. The reason for this is that in our model the bar-driven bending waves do not dissipate even after the initial source (buckling of the bar) disappears and the wave-like perturbations persist in the disk for tens of rotational periods (up to 4 Gyr). The bending waves (see Fig. 1) are not kinematical because they do not dissipate on the dynamical timescale. This has been predicted by (Darling & Widrow, 2019), who showed that self-gravity is crucial for the persistence of long-lived spontaneous bending waves in disks. Hence disk self-gravity is essential for the support of bending waves triggered by the bar buckling. That is why, even a very long time (≈ 3 Gyr) after the buckling of the bar $- z - v_z$ spiral patterns are clearly seen (see Fig. 2).

Acknowledgments

This work was granted access to the HPC resources of CINES under the allocation 2017-040507 (PI : P. Di Matteo) made by GENCI. This work has been sup-

ported by the ANR (Agence Nationale de la Recherche) through the MOD4Gaia project (ANR-15-CE31-0007, P.I.: P. Di Matteo). Numerical simulations are carried out with support by the Russian Science Foundation (project no. 19-72-20089) with using the equipment of the shared research facilities of HPC computing resources at Lomonosov Moscow State University supported by the project RFMEFI62117X0011. PB acknowledge the support by Chinese Academy of Sciences through the Silk Road Project at NAOC, through the ‘‘Qianren’’ special foreign experts program and also under the President’s International Fellowship for Visiting Scientists program of CAS. PB acknowledges the partial financial support of this work by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft through Collaborative Research Center (SFB 881) ‘‘The Milky Way System’’ (subproject Z2) at the Ruprecht-Karls-Universität Heidelberg. PB acknowledge the support of the Volkswagen Foundation under the Trilateral Partnerships grant No. 90411 and the special support by the NASU under the Main Astronomical Observatory GRID/GPU computing cluster project.

References

- Antoja, T., Helmi, A., Romero-Gómez, M., Katz, D., Babusiaux, C., et al. 2018, *Nature*, 561, 360.
- Athanassoula, E. 2005, *MNRAS*, 358, 1477.
- Binney, J. & Schönrich, R. 2018, *MNRAS*, 481, 1501.
- Bland-Hawthorn, J., Sharma, S., Tepper-García, T., Binney, J., Freeman, K.C., et al. 2019, *MNRAS*, 486, 1167.
- Cheng, X., Liu, C., Mao, S., & Cui, W. 2019, *ApJ*, 872, L1.
- Chequers, M.H. & Widrow, L.M. 2017, *MNRAS*, 472, 2751.
- Combes, F., Debbasch, F., Friedli, D., & Pfenniger, D. 1990, *A&A*, 233, 82.
- Darling, K. & Widrow, L.M. 2019, *MNRAS*, 484, 1050.
- Debattista, V.P., Carollo, C.M., Mayer, L., & Moore, B. 2004, *ApJL*, 604, L93.
- Fragkoudi, F., Di Matteo, P., Haywood, M., Khoperskov, S., Gomez, A., et al. 2017, *A&A*, 607, L4.
- Fragkoudi, F., Katz, D., White, S.D.M., Di Matteo, P., Trick, W., et al. 2019, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:1901.07568.
- Gaia Collaboration, Brown, A.G.A., Vallenari, A., Prusti, T., de Bruijne, J.H.J., et al. 2018a, *A&A*, 616, A1.
- Gaia Collaboration, Katz, D., Antoja, T., Romero-Gómez, M., Drimmel, R., et al. 2018b, *A&A*, 616, A11.
- Hunter, C. & Toomre, A. 1969, *ApJ*, 155, 747.
- Khoperskov, A., Bizyaev, D., Tiurina, N., & Butenko, M. 2010, *Astronomische Nachrichten*, 331, 731.
- Khoperskov, S. & Bertin, G. 2017, *A&A*, 597, A103.
- Khoperskov, S., Di Matteo, P., Gerhard, O., Katz, D., Haywood, M., et al. 2019, *A&A*, 622, L6.
- Kulsrud, R.M., Mark, J.W.K., & Caruso, A. 1971, *Ap&SS*, 14, 52.
- Laporte, C. F.P., Minchev, I., Johnston, K.V., & Gómez, F.A. 2019, *MNRAS*, 485, 3134.
- Li, Z.-Y. & Shen, J. 2019, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:1904.03314.
- Merritt, D. & Sellwood, J.A. 1994, *ApJ*, 425, 551.
- Michtchenko, T.A., Barros, D.A., Pérez-Villegas, A., & Lépine, J. R.D. 2019, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:1903.08325.
- Monari, G., Famaey, B., Siebert, A., Wegg, C., & Gerhard, O. 2018, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:1812.04151.
- Raha, N., Sellwood, J.A., James, R.A., & Kahn, F.D. 1991, *Nature*, 352, 411.
- Rodionov, S.A. & Sotnikova, N.Y. 2013, *MNRAS*, 434, 2373.
- Tian, H.-J., Liu, C., Wu, Y., Xiang, M.-S., & Zhang, Y. 2018, *ApJL*, 865, L19.
- Trick, W.H., Coronado, J., & Rix, H.-W. 2019, *MNRAS*, 484, 3291.
- Wang, C., Huang, Y., Yuan, H.B., Xiang, M.S., Chen, B.Q., et al. 2019, *ApJ*, 877, L7.